

Nationalism in Catvāri Śṛṅgā

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Abstract:

'Chatvāri Śṛṅgā' (literally meaning four horns) is a post-modern Sanskrit poetry by Prafulla Kumar Mishra, who is a prolific writer of many books in Sanskrit, Oriya and English. The post-modernist touch in this poetry is very vivid the matically and stylistically. In the poetry poet Prafulla Kumar Mishra are enumerated under four categories. They are: place, time, person, and condition. Respectively in this four dimensional world a person lives a four dimensional life. The poems are manifested as per the context. Therefore an air of freedom is exercised by the poet, not withstanding to any conformity. Mysticism, symbolism, spiritualism, nationalism and post-modernism have been rolled in to one. One can get many flavours while reading them sincerely. The extent has no limitation. Particularly in response to the influence of post-modernism, Poet has expressed nationalism in individual poems. The poems are mentioned below □

1. *Amaranātha Yātrī*
2. *Rudati Bhāratamātā*
3. *Kadā Bhārataḥ*
4. *Śoṇacumbanam*

The poet's recent picture shows the deep affection of homeland love. Many poets have tried to express nationalism as different as possible in the eyes but poet Prafulla Kumar Mishra is one of the recent modernists who has indentified the wounds and trauma of India, by touching the place of India's emotions and heritage, showed the country's ultimate humiliation.

(Keywords: Chatvāri Śṛṅgā, Post-modern, Nationalism, Post-modernism, Homeland, Heritage)

So far the term Nationalism in the western world is concerned, it is still obscure. The term is not yet defined. Israel Zangwill in his "Principle of Nationalities" says, - "Nationalism is one of those tropical jungles of thought in which politics and journalism flourish." H.L. Featherstone goes to say in his "A Century of Nationalism" as - "Nationalism is not capable of scientific definition." Most of the historians today agree upon the modern origin of Nationalism. G.P. Gooch remarks, - "Nationalism is a child of the French Revolution." On the other hand, Carlton J.H. Hayes remarks nationalism to be a very modern theory. He writes, - "Nationalism is modern, very modern."¹ John Oak smith describes nationalism as- "What the vast majority of civilized people feel to be the most sacred and dominating inspiration in life."² On the other hand, Max Weber tries to define the term as follows:- "Nationalism is a common bond of sentiment whose adequate expression would be a state of his own, and which, therefore, normally tends to give birth to such a state".

"If we closely observe the modern Sanskrit writings, we can see that the corpus of its theme is

remarkably wider. The poets of ancient and medieval period were confined to the eulogy of the deity, or the praise of the protagonist. However, now the modern Sanskrit poets are writing poems on the topics directly related to the contemporary issues like social, political as well as financial ups and downs, the problems of terrorism, corruption, unemployment etc. Sanskrit poets are writing on Gulf war, on corruption. They also have written on journey into desert. Among other modern themes which received attention today are patriotism, Nationality and other current affairs of our country. They write on freedom struggle and independence also"³

'Catvāri Śṛṅgā' (literally meaning four horns) is a post-modern Sanskrit poetry, containing 85 poems. In the poetry poet Prafulla Kumar Mishra are enumerated under four categories. They are: place, time, person, and condition. Respectively in this four dimensional world a person lives a four dimensional life. The extent has no limitation. Particularly in response to the influence of post-modernism, Poet has expressed nationalism in individual poems. The poet's recent picture shows the deep affection of homeland love. Many poets have tried to express nationalism as different as possible in the eyes but poet Prafulla Kumar Mishra is one of the recent modernists who has indentified the wounds and trauma of India, by touching the place of India's emotions and heritage, showed the country's ultimate humiliation.

1. *Amaranātha Yātrī* :

In this poem the poet is mentioned in the Amaranātha Pilgrimage. Amaranātha is the most

sacred pilgrim centre of the Hindus. Geographical and mythological traditions are contemporary view of the poet's imagination. Amarnātha is the mythological Hindu script according to Lord Śivā. He is also Mahādeva, simultaneously, the symbol of the killer and the protector, the valor and the vampire. Amaranātha journey is of the devotees in his vision, to seek immortality. Many obstacles of the journey of devotees are crossing terrorism, crossing torture, spent night and day in the cave exploring Amaranātha. In the words of the poet,-

रात्रिः गमिष्यति भविष्यति सुप्रभातम्
भास्वान् उदेष्यति हसिष्यति पङ्कजश्रीः
ईति विचिन्त्य रात्रौ स्थिते गुहायां
हा हताः वम्फोटेन दिवं प्रेरिताः ॥iv

Under the influence of spirits, in the poem sparks nationalism. Geographical location of Amaranātha is Jammu and Kashmir. The struggle to survive this most beautiful integral part of India is always going on. Amarnath's journey-pilgrimage, protection of India's integrity, geographical beauty, all can be enjoyed at the same time. According to mythology Lord Śivā had chosen Amaranātha for the teaching of immortality to Pārvaṭī. And today, Amaranātha journey is very important for the protection of national heritage and the integrity of India. Therefore, none of the pilgrims of Amaranātha, who are not Hindus, hold the integrity of all the Indians which carries the identity of nationalism.

2. Rudati Bhāratamātā :

The poem introduces the era of the stigma of India in the helplessness of the fellow countrymen, in the helplessness of the people. The poem is arranged in three stanzas respectively-failure to end the alliance, powerful helpless prisoner; the sadness of India's crushing voices in the face of humanity due to the laughter of hypocrisy lied to all the revived rivers of nationalism. So remembering the Indian past history and tradition of the poet the Indian Prisoner wanted freedom of India. Deep pains diminished and tears mixed with anger the poet said that-

कालिरुषिणी नृमुण्डमालिनी
अट्टहास्येन दिशः विकसिताः
त्रिपुरसुन्दरी त्रिपुरगामिनी
परमानन्दाभिवन्दिता ॥v

Wish to the heart criticize the people of India. With the greatest power the poet's crying has awakened the nation of nationality to the restoration of India's free spirited form.

In the name of the poem, the painting of the tears of nationalism is reflected in the mood. The principle of Indian culture and civilization are in the unification of diversity. In the present situation,

those people of India are sacrificing their past tradition without the danger and existence of all the regions. Indians forget the alliance, on the way to violence, the insidious and lousy chaos ruin omnipotence in the separation. So, the voice of the poet heard the tone of nationalism,-

दुःखःदुःखिताविगुणदर्शिता
चारसञ्चारविचारप्रचारैः
अपि मातस्तवाद्भुतक्षमता ॥vi

3. Kadā Bhārataḥ :

India's heritage is to protect integrity by establishing unity between diversity. Through the religion, script, tradition and history, the poet has sought to highlight the overall form of India in this poem. India land of truth and faith, keeping in mind the Indian tradition, the progressive all types of survival are protected from the accident. So it can be said in poet's language-

भविष्यन्तीति प्रचलिता कथा तथापि न मनः विस्मरेद्
व्यथाम्,
न कथ वदेत् न वा तुष्णीं भवेत् पीडा न सह्यते श्रुत्वा
दुर्घटनाम् ॥vii

The Indian people continued to remember the ancient heritage of India. Artistry, literature and art are all soft and tender in Indian literature. The poem is arranged in four stanzas respectively, Imagine the poet in the first stanza- in relation to teaching Mahābhārata Bhīṣma Lavpur story, second stanza-the importance of determining the present direction from India's past experience as a guide to true faith, third stanzas-artists, social workers, writers and judges show the correct instructions for the actions of people of all classes and the four stanzas- artistry, literature, art and culture all the past is only the strong fidelity of the poet on Indian civilization culture which is carries the identity of the nationalism of poetry.

The poetic poem in contemporary and tradition has seen the dynamic progress of India. Integration between Indian civilizations is culture, including education, art, literature and society. The poet has repeatedly warned that no sense of inattentiveness can lead to the separation of Indian culture. As the poet eyes,-

हालिकाः सैनिकाः सर्वे सेवकाः शिक्षकाः लिपिकाः तथा
विचारकाः

भारतमातुः सर्वे सैनिकाः-देश सवेयां सावधानता ॥viii

4. Śoṇacumbanam :

In the poem, the poet blood-stained presented the real transcript of an anarchical orthopedic society. In the first stanza- a woman has many male companions, many women's sexual intercourse with the charred men in fascination and delusion and illustrations of uncontrolled life such as alcohol addiction. In the second stanza- the

untimely demise of frustration, depression, the collapse of alliance in the debate, the alarming life the pregnant women reveals the great danger life. Anarchy, as defined in the third stanzas, children are also living outside the home crisis in terms of firing every day. As the poet says,-

प्रतिदिनं गुलिकाशब्देन
सद्योजातः शिशुपुत्रः प्रमोदितः
गृहे यत्र गूढचरः सन्त्रासवादस्य
भुशुण्ड्यग्रच्छुरिकया
मूकयति गृहस्य पुरुषान्
स्त्रियः मौनं नाटयन्ति।^{ix}

In such anarchy, the poet lauded the silence. The young people who embrace the new nation, the future and protector of the homeland, culture, society and civilization, today are engrossing in the path of terrorism by adopting extreme nationalism.

The patriotic poets awaken the troubled times for the recovery of healthy society civilization. As a bloody struggle, due to all the material things of the world, due to the rise of extremism, the society has become sick of civilization. Poet mocked the life of adulterers in order to cure the illness. So the poem carries the identity of healthy nationalism through the blood stream of extremist nationalism.

The theory of nationalism based upon political and economic foundation is new and obscure. On the other hand, the culture-based theory of Nationalism is perpetual and perfect. Forgetting the Indian heritage and history, the people and the statesmen have hindered the overall development of diverse India. India's dreams and hopes of Independence are dusting. In India, terrorism and bloodshed hurt India. Nationalism is losing people's mind day by day. The poet has kept these messages in order to awaken this nationalism. Critic of modern Sanskrit literature Dr. Arun Ranjan Mishra, overall, the focus of poetry is to give a holistic look- "Dr. P.K.Mishra's poems pulsate with all the genre of modernity. The rise of the intellectual man in modern age and his thoughtful being pervaded and even invaded by the types of cynicism, death of desire, pessimism, double mindedness, loneliness and aimlessness causes the thickly flowing emotion in his poetry. His main expertise, however, lies in his rare, ability of delving deep into the subconscious feelings and into a feeling of man's cosmic state, which propels to get into the region of god, and time stream"^x

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